

Report on the implementation of the survey with employers

Deliverable 6.1

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1. INTRODUCTORY REMARKS

The DignityFIRM project aims to better understand the realities of these sectors of the economy, which are vital for the food supply chain, referred to as F2F (Farm to Fork) sectors. Particular focus is placed on migrant workers, who have played a pivotal role in these labour-intensive sectors for decades. Their importance has become more evident since the pandemic (and in the case of selected countries has been intensified by labour shortages related to the full-scale war in Ukraine). The project has been designed to be both complex and overarching, covering migration and non-migration policies, socio-economic realities at various levels, and the well-being and dignity of migrant workers.

In this context, Work Package 6 (WP6) is particularly significant, as it focuses on two key areas: 1) the economic dimension of the process, and 2) employers and their employment choices. Based on the available theoretical and empirical literature, a model has been developed to conceptualise the factors responsible for the formal or informal employment of domestic and/or foreign workers (Chapter 2). This model considers cost-related conditions, market structure, and supply-side constraints. The next step was to use this model to design a survey for employers in four selected EU countries (Chapter 3), which was completed in the first half of 2025.

The main aim of this report is to describe the conceptualisation process in detail, with a particular focus on the implementation of the survey in Italy, the Netherlands, Poland and Spain (Chapter 4). Chapter 5 summarises the main results of the study, with the analysis referring to the companies surveyed, the scale and structure of migrant employment, and finally, informal employment (of both natives and migrants). The analysis of informal employment relies on two key elements, one of which is based on traditional survey methodology and the other on experimental design (list experiment and vignette experiment). The final parts of the report discuss the limitations of the study and summarise.

2. THEORETICAL AND CONCEPTUAL BACKGROUND

The main motivation behind the survey and projected analyses was to gain a better understanding of the main drivers for employing foreigners and natives, and how this is done formally and informally. This objective poses some conceptual and theoretical challenges as it links two extensive bodies of literature that largely remain separate. The first strand of literature primarily refers to the form of employment and discusses the reasons for employing workers formally or informally (most of these studies are microeconomic). The second strand is far more interdisciplinary, attempting to understand the origins of the employment of foreigners and why immigrants are commonly overrepresented in informal jobs.

According to La Porta and Shleifer (2014), economic research provides three main views of informality: 1) informality is the result of excessive government regulations that prevent potentially productive entrepreneurs from engaging in formal economic activity; 2) informality is a rational decision by employers to avoid taxes and regulations; and 3) informality is a survival strategy employed by low-skilled entrepreneurs who are too unproductive to engage in formal economic activity even if entry barriers to the formal sector were removed. The third explanation implies the coexistence of two separate economic sectors: the formal sector, which is capital intensive, and the informal sector, which is labour intensive (and these sectors do not necessarily compete with each other in terms of production). This duality is used to explain the segmentation of the labour market between different economic sectors (for example, in Piore's (1979) dual labour market theory). The microeconomic literature primarily focuses on the first two explanations, considering cost implications (Schneider and Enste, 2000; Schneider and Buehn, 2018), the trade-offs between the costs and benefits of informal employment (Di Porto et al., 2017), industrial organisation (firm size and productivity) (Erosa et al., 2023; Kanbur, 2017; Ulyssea, 2018; Vallanti and Gianfreda, 2021), as well as skills and workers' strategies (Galiani and Weinschelbaum, 2011; Taymaz, 2023). We argue that these considerations should be complemented by a broader discussion of the so-called concealment costs faced by both employers and workers (Kolm and Larsen, 2019), as well as the moral issues related to particular forms of economic activity (Mickiewicz et al., 2019; De Backer et al., 2015).

The second strand of literature is also extensive. In general, it concludes that the informal employment of migrants results from the interaction of two key factors: 1) restrictive legislation that limits opportunities for formal employment, both for employers, who must fulfil many formalities and incur costs, and for employees, who are unlikely to be employed formally if they do not have specific legal status and 2) the ever-present incentive for employers to reduce labour costs and avoid taxes and social contributions (Boswell and Straubhaar, 2004). The latter remains a problem, particularly in industries impacted by natural variations, such as agriculture, or those that compete fiercely due to global influences and growing rivalry, such as manufacturing and

tourism. From an economic perspective, the optimal level of informal labour would exceed zero in several economic sectors. This is partly due to the fact that business-friendly governments may be strongly incentivised to tolerate these kinds of informal activities (Boswell and Straubhaar, 2004; Reyneri, 1998; Ambrosini, 2016; Ambrosini and Hajer, 2023; Bommès and Sciortino, 2011; Talani, 2019).

While conceptualising the model, we referred to both strands of literature and attempted to link them in an innovative and beneficial way. Departing from a neoclassical economic approach, these works consider the various factors discussed above when employers hire workers, while also taking into account the particular institutional setting (thus covering both neoclassical and institutional arguments). Additionally, it was assumed that controlling for employer attitudes towards tax evasion and migrants was necessary. To better assess the above effects, an experimental approach (vignette experiment) was envisaged to identify the preferences of both natives and immigrants regarding formal and informal employment.

The conceptual model is as follows: Firstly, it is assumed that an employer can choose to hire migrants or natives in a compliant or non-compliant manner, resulting in four possible combinations. Secondly, the decision to hire a migrant or a native may be influenced by preferences, but may also result from labour market constraints, especially on the supply side. The decision to offer jobs in a compliant or non-compliant manner is expected to be the result of an economic analysis that also takes into account concealment costs, which may be non-monetary (in particular, the cost of evading norms).

The most important decision factors for employers are therefore (In parentheses is the sign of the effect, showing whether a specific category of migrants or compliant workers makes employers more (+) or less (-) 'attractive' within a specific category):

1. Cost considerations

- a. WAGES: Migrants (+) are willing to accept lower wages. Compliant employment requires higher wages, fulfilment of minimum wage requirements, social security costs, taxes, etc.
- b. HIRING COSTS: Recruitment is more complicated for compliant employment (-), but migrants are more readily available in some sectors (+). This may depend on the employer's specific situation (existing networks, sector), but also on the skill requirements.
- c. Administrative costs: Compliant employment leads to a higher administrative burden, especially for migrant employees.
- d. Stability of worker relations: Training costs for migrants (possibly -). This may depend on the employer's specific situation (e.g. existing staff who may be able to train immigrants in their native language).
- e. CONCEALMENT COSTS: Non-compliant employment leads to higher concealment costs, in terms of potential fines and non-pecuniary costs such as not conforming to social norms (depending on their strength).

f. RISKS: In the event of adverse outcomes (e.g. drought), there will be greater losses for compliant employment (-).

2. Addressing labour market imperfections/supply-side constraints

a. SUPPLY in general: Migrants (usually in agriculture) and natives may or may not be available.

b. FLEXIBILITY OF SUPPLY: Migrants may be willing and able to work longer hours or seasonally. Compliant workers are tied to specific contracts, which are more difficult to resolve for both employers and employees. This may have a positive or negative effect.

c. BARGAINING POWER: Immigrants (+) have reduced bargaining power, particularly if their legal status depends on their work status. Compliant native workers (-), however, have more bargaining power.

Furthermore, it was assumed that employment-related decisions are made within an institutional setting, where the most important dimensions are:

1. Market competition (external constraints).
2. Contracts to be fulfilled (firm-specific constraints).
3. Law and law enforcement
4. Social norms (tax morality).

The magnitude of the effect of these factors is likely to be influenced by firm size, productivity and sector.

All of the above factors informed the construction of the survey and will also be referred to in the analytical phase, particularly with regard to the experimental part (with a set of pre-registered hypotheses and research questions).

3. SURVEY DESIGN

Following the above considerations the key aims of the study were to:

- identify the main economic and labour market factors that employers consider in their decisions to hire migrants and natives, in a compliant and non-compliant way,
- assess the relative importance of these factors,
- and verify whether there exists a trade-off value between formal and informal employment of migrant and native workers.

The survey was conducted as a computer-aided telephone interview (CATI), with an optional web version (CAWI) should a respondent prefer this way of answering questions. The goal was to conduct at least 300 interviews in each of the four countries, with at least 70 interviews conducted in each of three selected sectors:

- Agriculture (A01 and A03, except A01.15 – agriculture and fishing, except tobacco cultivation), hereafter “Agriculture”;
- Food processing (C10 except C10.9 – food processing, except for the production of feed and animal food), hereafter “Food processing”;
- Bars and Restaurants (I56 gastronomy), hereafter “Food service”.

The studied population consisted of firms in the above-mentioned sectors, employing at least 1 paid worker (i.e., excluding the owner) and at most 49 workers.

The questionnaire consisted of a screening part (to identify the firm sector and firm size, as well as the eligibility of the respondent who was supposed to have knowledge about employment of workers), a set of questions related to obtaining consent to participate in the survey and provide information about the research project, and 27 questions related to the research hypotheses posed. The majority of these questions were in traditional form, related to the size and structure of employment of natives and foreigners, employment conditions and market conditions.

Three of the basic questions were related to informal employment (Q12 – about the documents on the basis of which migrants were employed; Q23 – about health insurance of migrant workers; Q30 – about whether it occurred in the firm that a person was employed before formalities were fulfilled in “urgent” cases). Additional questions were related to preferences towards hiring migrant workers. Furthermore, two questions (Q24 and Q25) were related to morality (attitude towards tax evasion and the country’s institutions).

The questionnaire differed for firms which employed foreigners and those who did not, with the first group answering additional questions (related to the countries of origin of foreign workers and their gender composition, the legal forms of employment of migrants, a comparison of wages

of migrants and natives) and sub-questions (related to job characteristics, asked separately for natives and foreigners).

Importantly, the core of the survey consisted of two experiments, where questions were randomized between respondents. The first experiment – a so-called list experiment, whose goal was to assess the scale of informal employment – was a question where respondents were asked to specify how many (but not which specifically) elements of a list were true regarding their firm. The respondents were randomly assigned to three groups: a control group, who received a list consisting of 5 elements, and two test groups, to whom a list consisting of 6 elements was presented. For test group 1, the list consisted of the 5 control elements and a statement that a native worker was hired without fulfilling all formalities; for test group 2, the list consisted of the same 5 elements and a statement that a migrant worker was hired without fulfilling all formalities. Firms employing foreigners were randomly assigned into one of the three groups; firms which did not report foreigners were randomly assigned into the control group and test group 1.

The second experiment was a discrete choice vignette study. Each respondent was asked to answer a block of four questions related to a hypothetical situation of hiring a new worker. Respondents were randomly assigned to one of 10 questionnaire versions for Poland and the Netherlands, where the versions did not differ between sectors, or one of 27 questionnaire versions for Italy and Spain, where the versions were differentiated between sectors (9 per sector). In the latter case, the need for differentiation stemmed from the fact that in different sectors, significantly different wage levels (in particular, minimum wages) are observed. In the choice experiment, the respondents were presented with choices between two unnamed alternatives. The alternative attributes included: the type of worker (native, migrant from EU, migrant from outside of EU), the type of contract (permanent/temporary), the hourly wage related to the contract, as well as information on whether the contract is formal or not; in the latter case, the level of a potential fine for informal employment was also specified. The choice sets were generated to allow estimation of main effects of the attributes as well as the interaction between the type of worker, whether the employment is formal, and the wage level. The goal of this experiment was to assess the “value” of formal/informal employment of natives / immigrants (to reveal the mechanisms of non-compliant migrant employment).

Preliminary versions of the questionnaire were piloted in the four countries (two interviews each in Poland, Spain and Italy, one interview in the Netherlands). After the pilot, question phrasing was adjusted. During the actual survey, the functioning of the questionnaire in general and the choice experiment in particular were assessed in each country after collecting 30 interviews. In the Netherlands, the initial survey design needed adjustments (new choice sets were generated).

4. SURVEY IMPLEMENTATION

The survey with employers was coordinated by the Centre of Migration Research at the University of Warsaw and conducted by Escarola sp. z o.o in four countries: Italy, the Netherlands, Poland and Spain. In this section we provide basic information related to the surveying process, including details on the sampling frame and the database used in the study (4.1), basic data on the implementation of the survey in the four studied countries (4.2), as well as information related to quality control (4.3).

4.1. SAMPLING FRAMES

The sampling frame for the survey was the Dun & Bradstreet (D&B) firm dataset. D&B's database is one of the largest and oldest global databases on companies and businesses. It contains financial, commercial, structural and creditworthiness information on companies from around the world, and covers more than 500 million companies worldwide, including micro and small businesses. D&B works with a variety of sources, including trade registries, credit reports, financial institutions and insurance companies. The data is updated regularly, although the frequency may vary by country and company.

The representativeness of the D&B databases can vary - especially for smaller companies or companies in emerging markets, data may be incomplete. Data is partly declarative - not all companies provide full financial data, so in such cases, D&B analyses may be based on estimates. Under GDPR regulations, individuals have the right to exercise their right to be forgotten, and D&B, complying with these regulations, is forced to remove such records from the service. This has the greatest impact when it comes to the A01 and A03 sectors, as these types of entities are most often run by individuals. In a standard procedure, if a record is included in the D&B registry, the entrepreneur is informed of this fact and any further decisions about remaining in the database are at his discretion. D&B does not have statistics to show what are the tendencies among entrepreneurs in the sectors used in this study, but many choose to leave their data in the D&B database.

D&B monitors registries and official publications on an ongoing basis and uses automated third-party tools, technologies and services to ensure that data is up-to-date. D&B assures that its dataset reflects the current official status, but does not provide a complete list of companies in the database. Only the total number of records in the database is disclosed.

The records for this study were obtained from D&B and were drawn at random from their databases at the following dates:

for Poland: March 17 and April 3 (additional sample)
for the Netherlands: April 2

for Italy: April 2
for Spain: April 2.

4.1.1. Database for Poland

According to available data from the Central Statistical Office (CSO) in Poland, at the end of 2024 in Poland, 97.0% of the companies employed fewer than 10 persons, 2.4% of the companies employed between 10 and 49 persons, 0.6% of companies employed more than 49 individuals. Therefore, by constraining the sample to firms employing at most 49 workers, we exclude a very small share of firms.

Companies in Poland employing 1-49 workers in the specified sectors (after D&B):

- A01 and A03 (except A01.15) ~120,313
- C10 (except C10.9) ~25,398
- I56 ~61,435.

Details on the records purchased and the employment structure in the purchased databased are included in APPENDIX (A2)

4.1.2. Database for the Netherlands

According to available data from the Central Statistical Office (CBS) in the Netherlands, at the end of 2024 in the Netherlands 96.9% of the companies employed fewer than 10 persons, 2.4% of companies employed between 10 and 49 persons, 0.7% of the companies employed more than 49 persons. Therefore, similarly to Poland, by constraining the sample to firms employing at most 49 workers, the share of excluded companies is very low.

Companies in the Netherlands employing 1-49 people in given sectors (after CBS):

- A01 and A03 (except A01.15) ~ 155,610
- C10 (except C10.9) ~ 7,570
- I56 ~ 68,555.

Details on the records purchased and the employment structure in the purchased databased are included in APPENDIX (A2)

4.1.3 Database for Italy

According to available Istat data, at the end of 2024 in Italy 93.3% of the companies employed fewer than 10 workers, 5.8% of the companies employed between 10 and 49 individuals, 0.9% of the companies employed more than 49 people. This means that the situation in this case is similar

to Poland and the Netherlands – by constraining the sample to firms employing at most 49 workers, we exclude a very small share of firms. Companies in Italy employing 1-49 people in given sectors (after Istat):

- A01 and A03 (except A01.15) ~ 421,161
- C10 (except C10.9) ~ 753,884
- I56 ~ 249,562.

Details on the records purchased and the employment structure in the purchased databased are included in APPENDIX (A2).

4.1.4. Database for Spain

According to available data from the National Statistics Institute (INE) in Spain, at the end of 2024 in Spain 94.5% of the companies employed fewer than 10 individuals, 4.7% of the companies employed between 10 and 49 workers, 0.8% of the companies employed more than 49 people. Therefore, by constraining the sample to firms employing at most 49 workers, we exclude a very small share of firms, and this is exactly the same case as presented before.

Companies in Spain employing 1-49 people in the sectors concerned (after INE):

- A01 and A03 (except A01.15) ~ 71,351
- C10 (except C10.9) ~ 24,113
- I56 ~ 281,297.

Details on the records purchased and the employment structure in the purchased databased are included in APPENDIX (A2).

4.2. IMPLEMENTATION OF THE SURVEY

4.2.1. Poland

In Poland, the training of interviewers was conducted on March 19, 2025, followed by the implementation of the survey, which took place from March 20 to April 24, 2025. A total of 11 interviewers were involved in the process, completing 300 interviews, resulting in a 100% sample completion rate. The methodology used was CATI, with all 300 interviews conducted through CATI and none via the CAWI method. Table 1 shows how the completed interviews were distributed across the different sectors.

Table 1. Completed interviews in Poland by sector

Sectors	Total
Agriculture	91
Food processing	109
Food service	100
Overall	300

Source: Own elaboration based on information provided by the surveying company.

The response rate (see Table 2) was, on average, 5.6%, with little variance between particular subsectors.

Table 2. Response rate in Poland, by sector

	Response rate
Agriculture	6.0%
Food processing	5.8%
Food service	5.0%
Overall	5.6%

Source: Own elaboration based on information provided by the surveying company.

As shown in Table A13 in the Appendix, the main reasons for the lack of contact were either no response or incorrect contact, the latter being a consequence of the database structure. In the case of companies that refused to be surveyed, lack of time was the main reason, along with a set of additional reasons provided. The dominating reasons for refusal were:

- Lack of time, especially in the food service sector;
- Limited number of company employees who could answer the survey questions, and
- Company policy prohibited participation in such surveys.

The main issues of concern were:

- Questions about the employment status of foreign workers;
- The length of the survey: the number of questions requiring full concentration made the interview process time-consuming, and respondents wanted to reduce the time spent on the survey;
- Concerns about anonymity.

The details of the sample and the implementation process can be found in Appendix A3.

4.2.2. The Netherlands

In the Netherlands, the training of interviewers was conducted on April 9, 2025, and the survey was implemented between April 14 and May 19, 2025. A total of 11 interviewers participated in the study, completing 304 interviews, which resulted in a 100% sample completion rate. The methodology used primarily CATI interviewing, with 292 interviews conducted via CATI and 12 via CAWI.

The APPENDIX (A3) contains the details of the sample and the implementation process. Below we discuss just selected characteristics.

Table 3. Completed interviews in the Netherlands by sector

Sectors	Total
Agriculture	110
Food processing	80
Food service	114
Total	304

Source: Own elaboration based on information provided by the surveying company.

Table 3 shows the distribution of completed interviews by subsector, with the largest number of interviews completed in the food service sector. The overall response rate was 22.2%. Table A18 in the appendix presents the main reasons why interviews were not conducted. In cases of lack of contact, the main reason was no answer; in cases of records contacted, refusal to participate in the study was the key factor.

The main reasons for refusal were:

- Overly sensitive questions: many respondents felt that some questions were too personal, particularly those concerning employment contracts, hiring practices or terms and conditions of employment;
- Lack of time: many respondents were too busy to participate, especially in the food service sector, where potential participants were often working during the hours when calls were made.

The following were indicated as key issues of concern:

- Difficulty scheduling interviews: many people were busy or at work, requiring appointments to be rescheduled, sometimes multiple times.
- Interrupted interviews: some interviews were terminated early because respondents felt uncomfortable with certain topics.
- Reluctance to share information: some respondents were hesitant or unwilling to discuss details about their workplace.

4.2.3. Italy

In Italy, the training of interviewers was held on April 10, 2025, followed by the implementation of the survey, which took place from April 11 to May 13, 2025. A total of 10 interviewers participated in the survey, successfully completing 300 interviews, resulting in a 100% sample completion rate. The methodology used was CATI, with all 300 interviews conducted via CATI and none through CAWI.

Table 4. Completed interviews in Italy by sector

Sectors	Total
Agriculture	99
Food processing	100
Food service	101
Total	300

Source: Own elaboration based on information provided by the surveying company.

Table 4 shows that, based on the assumptions, the interviews were evenly distributed across the subsectors. A response rate of 23.6% was achieved.

Table A23 in the appendix provides details of the contacting process, showing that the main reason for lack of response was simply that there was no answer, and that there were serious issues with arranging appointments. In the case of refusals, the main reasons were the following:

- Overly sensitive questions: many respondents felt that some questions were too personal, particularly those concerning employment contracts, hiring practices or terms and conditions of employment;
- Lack of time: Many respondents were too busy to participate, particularly in the food service sector, where potential participants were often working during the hours when calls were made.

The key issues of concern that arose were as follows:

- Difficulty scheduling interviews – many people were busy or at work, requiring appointments to be rescheduled, sometimes multiple times;
- Interrupted interviews: some interviews were terminated early because respondents felt uncomfortable with certain topics;
- Reluctance to share information: some respondents were reluctant or unwilling to discuss details about their workplace.

Comprehensive details pertaining to the sample and the implementation process are included in the APPENDIX (A3).

4.2.4. Spain

In Spain, the training of interviewers was conducted on April 14, 2025, and the survey was carried out from April 16 to May 7, 2025. A total of 9 interviewers participated, completing 301 interviews, which resulted in a 100% sample completion rate. The survey was conducted using the CATI method, with all 301 interviews completed via CATI and none through the CAWI method.

Table 5. Completed interviews in Spain by sector

Sectors	Total
Agriculture	98
Food processing	100
Food service	103
Total	301

Source: Own elaboration based on information provided by the surveying company.

The sectoral structure of completed interviews is presented in Table 5; a response rate of 18.2% was achieved.

Table A28 (see Appendix) provides detailed information on the contact process. It reveals that the main reason for lack of contact was the lack of opportunity (no response). In cases where companies were contacted but an interview was still not possible, issues with appointments and refusals to participate in the study played a key role. The main reasons for refusal included:

- Many respondents felt that some questions were too personal, particularly those concerning employment contracts, hiring practices, or terms and conditions of employment, suggesting that overly sensitive questions were being asked.
- Lack of time was cited as a reason for non-participation, with many respondents, especially those in the food service sector, being too busy to take part, often because they were working during the hours when calls were made.

People expressed the following as the main issues of concern:

- Difficulty in arranging interviews – a lot of people were either busy or at work, which meant that appointments often had to be rearranged, sometimes more than once.
- Some interviews were terminated early because respondents felt uncomfortable with certain topics, and there were also interruptions to the interviews.
- Reluctance to share information. Some respondents were hesitant. Others were unwilling. They did not want to discuss details about their workplace.

Comprehensive details pertaining to the sample and the implementation process may be found in the APPENDIX (A3).

4.3. QUALITY CONTROL PROCEDURES

As part of the quality control procedures, interviewers underwent standardized online training that covered both substantive and technical aspects of the survey. In Poland, this training was conducted in the presence of the CMR to ensure alignment with expectations. Prior to the start of fieldwork, interviewers completed knowledge tests and participated in sample interviews to become familiar with the test version of the questionnaire and accompanying materials. Just before the survey launch, a final knowledge check was conducted by the CATI Supervisor. Interviewers also received specific guidance on how to schedule interviews and identify the appropriate respondents within the target companies.

To ensure data quality, all interviews had the potential to be recorded, and supervisors monitored at least 10% of the interviews daily to verify adherence to instructions. Any interviews that did not meet the required quality standards were repeated—six in Poland and two in the Netherlands—making them the only rejected interviews during the entire survey. Additional

attention was given to ensuring interviewers could adjust their language and communication style appropriately for senior-level business respondents.

The quality control process also included an analysis of interview duration and logical consistency in responses. Interviewers had the ability to re-contact respondents to clarify vague, incomplete, or ambiguous answers. The CATI/CAWI system featured built-in script logic checks with automated validations to ensure appropriate value ranges, logical transitions, and internal consistency. Before the full launch, the questionnaire was thoroughly inspected and tested for content coherence, flow, and linguistic clarity. As mentioned above, a pilot study was conducted to test the script and survey instrument on a small scale, which led to final refinements. Ongoing oversight was provided by the CMR, including modifications to experimental questions in the Netherlands based on findings from the pilot phase.

5. MAIN RESULTS AND FINDINGS

5.1. THE OVERALL CONDITION OF FIRMS

In what follows, the results of the survey are presented by country, rather than by sector, unless important sectoral differences emerge. This is due to the fact that the results were found to be most influenced by the situation in specific countries rather than sectors. Unless stated otherwise, the questions referred to the situation in 2024, that is the year preceding the survey.

The overall condition of the firms interviewed has been assessed as good in all the countries that have been surveyed. The percentage of firms experiencing rising turnovers in 2024 ranged from 30% of firms in Poland to 58% in the Netherlands. The percentage of firms experiencing turnovers similar to those registered in the previous year ranged from 29% in the Netherlands to 56% in Spain. On the aggregate level, only one firm in eight declared a decrease in turnover. At the same time, over 80% of firms in each country (ranging from 82% in Italy and the Netherlands to 88% in Poland) did not significantly increase their scale of operations or the size of their workforce in 2024. In Italy, the Netherlands and Poland almost three companies out of ten, and two out of ten in Italy introduced technological innovations that enable work automation. These innovations were the most frequent in the sector of food processing, and the least so in food service.

The majority of companies surveyed encountered relevant obstacles to conducting business; the percentage of firms declaring no such obstacles ranged from 7% in Spain to 22% in Poland, and from 10% in food processing (four countries together) to 16% in food service. The main obstacles were the cost aspects of firms' functioning, that is inflation and costs of raw materials (from 41% of firms declaring this obstacle in Italy to 64% in Spain) and labour costs (from 34% in Italy to 60% in Poland). Taxes and regulations were also important impediments, especially in Italy where three out of four firms pointed to this obstacle. Lack of human resources hindered doing business to a lesser extent: this obstacle was selected by only 15% of firms in Italy, 20% in the Netherlands, 31% in Poland and 36% in Spain.

Figure 1. The main obstacles to doing business by country (in percent)

Source: Own elaboration based on DignityFIRM survey.

5.2. THE EMPLOYMENT OF MIGRANTS

Depending on the country surveyed, the percentage of enterprises that employed at least one migrant (foreign) worker, for any period of time in 2024 and on any terms, ranged from 35% in Poland to 79% in Italy (Figure 2). These differences were less relevant across sectors, with shares amounting to 54% of firms in food processing, 56% in agriculture and 60% in food service. The majority of companies that employed migrant workers at some point in 2024, employed up to four migrants. This finding is related to the overall size of the firms in the survey (not exceeding 49).

Figure 2. The percentage of enterprises employing at least one migrant worker

Source: Own elaboration based on DignityFIRM survey.

Migrant workers were in majority women. The directions of mobility remained diverse between the countries studied. In Italy and Spain, companies with migrant workforce often selected Morocco, Romania and the countries of Sub-Saharan Africa as the main origins. Italian companies pointed also to Bangladesh and Pakistan as important countries of origin, whereas the Spanish firms selected Colombia and Venezuela in this context. Firms in the Netherlands recruited migrants mostly from Poland, Romania and Ukraine, and to a lower extent, Bulgaria and Turkey. In turn, the vast majority (79%) of the Polish companies with migrant workforce selected Ukraine as the country of origin of their foreign employees.

Migrants were employed primarily as skilled or unskilled manual workers. In the overall sample of four countries, one company with foreign workforce in two employed migrants as skilled manual workers, and as many as nine companies in ten employed migrants as unskilled manual workers. Migrant skilled employment was more frequent in food service (62% of firms with migrant workforce in all four countries) than in food processing (54%) and agriculture (34%), whereas migrant unskilled employment was more frequent in agriculture (94%) and food processing (90%) than in food service (79%).

The Dutch and Polish employers declared in majority that at such posts the labour costs were the same for migrants and national workers. This concerned also skilled manual posts in Italy. In turn, in reference to unskilled manual posts in Italy, as well as skilled and unskilled manual posts in Spain three employers out of ten declared lower labour costs of foreigners (and six out of ten declared the same costs). This suggests that employers' migrant-hiring strategies in these countries were aimed at reducing labour costs by employing migrants.

The indicators pointing to permanent, full-time employment approximate to some extent the reliance of surveyed firms on migrant workforce. In all four countries (Figure 3) and two sectors: food processing and food service (Figure 4), the majority of firms with migrant workforce declared permanent and full-time employment of migrants. In agriculture, the majority of employers resorted to migrant workers seasonally, but also on full-time basis. Non-standard forms of employment, that is through temporary employment agencies or migrant self-employment depend on the national, rather than sectoral specificity. Employment through temporary employment agencies takes place most frequently in the Netherlands and Spain, whereas self-employment occurs most frequently in the Netherlands.

The recruitment of migrant workers takes place mostly through informal recommendations and labour exchanges, temporary work agencies and, in the Netherlands and Poland, mass media and social media (Figure 5). These recruitment methods are different in the case of national workers, for whom the role of external recruitment agencies and temporary work agencies is less relevant, and employers have relied more frequently on internal recruitment units, mass media and social media, job centres and public employment agencies.

Figure 3. Types of employment and working hours for migrants employed in enterprises with at least one migrant worker, by country, as percentage of firms

Source: Own elaboration based on DignityFIRM survey.

Figure 4. Types of employment and working hours for migrants employed in enterprises with at least one migrant worker, by sector, as percentage of firms

Source: Own elaboration based on DignityFIRM survey.

Figure 5. Recruitment means for migrant workers, by country, as percentage of firms with migrant workers

Source: Own elaboration based on DignityFIRM survey.

Our survey shows that, over the next year, companies in the food sector do not intend to hire foreigners: 27% of companies in Spain, 17% in Italy and Poland, and 14% in the Netherlands declared such an intention (Figure 6). However, many companies do not rule out the possibility of employing migrants: 37–38% in Poland and Spain, 52% in Italy, and 58% in the Netherlands. The intention or the possibility of hiring a migrant is consistent across all surveyed sectors; only in agriculture, one company out of four ruled out the possibility of hiring a foreigner.

Figure 6. Plans of companies to employ a migrant worker in 2025, by sector of activity or country

Source: Own elaboration based on DignityFIRM survey.

All companies, whether or not they employed foreign workers, were asked about their preferences regarding the nationality of a new employee in a hypothetical situation where they were hiring

someone. In Italy and the Netherlands, the majority of firms declared they do not consider whether the candidates were natives or migrants (Table 6); in turn, in Poland and Spain the responses were evenly distributed between looking for native workers in the first place, and not considering the candidate's nationality. In the sectoral breakdown, two out of three firms in agriculture and food service would not consider whether the candidate was native or foreign, whereas one firm in three would look primarily for natives. In food processing, firms would not consider the nationality (54%) or look primarily for natives (42%), which suggests a slightly higher propensity among employers in this sector to hire native workers.

Table 6. Responses to typical practices of hiring new workers by country, as percentage of all companies surveyed

	Country				
	Italy	the Netherlands	Poland	Spain	Total
primarily looking for native workers	28.67	19.00	55.45	46.51	37.46
primarily looking for foreigners	6.33	0.67	0.33	3.65	2.74
not consider whether the candidates are native workers or foreigners	65.00	80.33	44.22	49.83	59.80
Total	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00

Source: Own elaboration based on DignityFIRM survey.

All companies were asked about the potential reasons for hiring foreign workers instead of native ones. Altogether, 46% of respondents did not identify any particular reason for employing foreign workers. However, respondents were allowed to select an unlimited number of reasons for hiring migrant workers in their companies (Table 7). Dutch respondents were the least likely to indicate any reason for employing migrant workers. All countries together, the most frequently indicated reason was the limited number of native workers willing to apply for jobs (33%), and the fact that foreigners accept employment in more flexible forms (27%). In Italy and Spain, it was also important that foreigners accept lower wages.

Table 7. Reasons for employing foreign workers by country, as percentage of all companies surveyed

	Country				
	Italy	the Netherlands	Poland	Spain	Total
not enough native workers apply for the job	40	17	30	45	33
foreigners accept lower wages	22	3	8	35	17
foreigners accept employment in more flexible forms	42	9	16	42	27
foreigners work better	16	5	3	15	10
foreigners have specific qualifications	3	7	16	16	10
majority of applications are foreign	26	4	9	2	16

Source: Own elaboration based on DignityFIRM survey.

In a similar question, companies were asked to select a reason against employing a foreigner. The percentage of companies that declared no such reason ranged from 65-67% in Italy and Poland, 78% in Spain to 85% in the Netherlands. Again, respondents were allowed to select an unlimited number of reasons against hiring migrant workers in their companies (Table 8). The most important were: communication problems with native colleagues (45% companies selected this reason in the four countries together) or customers (35%), cultural differences (22%) and, in all countries except the Netherlands, time required to obtain necessary documentation for hiring a migrant (20%).

Table 8. Reasons against employing foreign workers by country, as percentage of all companies surveyed

	Country				
	Italy	the Netherlands	Poland	Spain	Total
language difficulties in communicating between foreigners and native workers	23	73	45	38	45
cultural differences	24	9	18	36	22
the time it takes to obtain documentation to employ a foreigner	20	4	24	32	20
the costs of obtaining documentation to employ a foreigner	11	3	15	21	13
foreigners have higher salary expectations	2	1	8	5	4
difficulties in using/adapting competencies acquired in another country	13	2	11	25	13
native workers do not want to work with foreigners	11	5	8	13	9
bad experience with foreign workers in the past	11	4	12	16	10
difficulties in finding housing for foreigners	14	6	16	20	14
language communication problems with customers	12	74	36	18	35

Source: Own elaboration based on DignityFIRM survey.

5.3. INFORMAL EMPLOYMENT

As signalled above, three non-experimental questions in the questionnaire were related to informal employment:

- Question about the documents on the basis of which migrants were employed;
- Question about health insurance of migrant workers;
- Question about whether it occurred in the firm that a person was employed before formalities were fulfilled in “urgent” cases

When asked directly about the types of documents used, the majority of employers indicated documents signalling legal forms of migrant employment, with only marginal shares (0%-4%) indicating the “other” option, indirectly suggesting a possibility that employment may have been informal (Table 9). These numbers are certainly biased, as in such a question, respondents may obviously be unwilling to disclose the truth.

Table 9. Share of firms employing foreigners based on specific types of documents, by country (in percent)

	Country			
	Italy	Netherlands	Poland	Spain
Work permit	68.49	32.59	56.07	67.96
Seasonal work permit	12.61	5.93	9.35	51.46
Contract of service, posted workers	2.10	66.67	36.45	17.96
Student visa or family-based permit	2.10	6.67	4.67	18.45
Refugee status and temporary protection	30.25	24.44	25.23	7.28
Documents of EU-citizens	20.59	18.52	6.54	37.86
Employer's statement on entrusting work (PL)	0.00	0.00	21.50	0.00
Long-term residence permit (IT)	47.90	0.00	0.93	0.00
Other	0.84	2.22	3.74	0.00

Source: Own elaboration based on DignityFIRM survey.

In response to the question related to health insurance of migrant workers, the majority of employers (74% for Spain, 76% for Italy, 84% for the Netherlands and 93% for Poland) indicated that all of their migrant workers have health insurance (Table 10). The remaining part of employers either indicated that not all of their migrant employees have health insurance (or “not yet”) – thus suggesting informal employment – or that they do not know. The latter response could be justified if a firm employed workers through a temporary employment agency and was not in charge of the documentation, but in the sample, this does not appear to be related, as firms

indicating such employment forms and those who do not, have similar shares of “don’t know” answers. Nevertheless, part of the fraction may be attributed to the usage of agencies.

However, what should be stressed is that the relatively high share of employers indicating all migrants have health insurance in Poland may still include irregular employment, as in this country Ukrainians with temporary protection status have automatic health insurance regardless of whether they are employed formally, and as mentioned above, the majority of foreign employees in Poland are Ukrainian.

Table 10. Responses to the question related to foreign employees having health insurance, by country (in percent)

	Country			
	Italy	Netherlands	Poland	Spain
yes, all of them	75.63	84.44	92.52	74.27
yes, some of them	19.33	2.22	2.80	21.84
no, they do not, but an appropriate procedure is under way	2.94	2.22	0.00	0.97
no, they do not	0.42	0.74	0.93	0.00
I don't know	1.68	10.37	3.74	2.91
Total	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00

Source: Own elaboration based on DignityFIRM survey.

The last non-experimental question was related to cases of employment “before all formalities were fulfilled” (of both migrants and natives). In all countries under study, if employment was regular, this should not have been the case. Meanwhile, around 9% (Poland), 10% (the Netherlands), 21% (Spain) and 32% (Italy) respondents among firms employing migrants admitted to this happening in their companies, with up to 10% more (Spain) not ruling out such a possibility (Table 11). Therefore, based on the responses to this question, one may assess that approximately 10% (Poland, Netherlands) to 30% (Spain, Italy) companies employing migrants in the studied sectors were engaged in employment which was not fully compliant (of both migrants and natives).

Table 11. Share of firms employing “before formalities are fulfilled”, by country (in percent) – firms employing migrants

	Country			
	Italy	Netherlands	Poland	Spain
yes	32.35	10.37	9.35	21.36
no	67.23	89.63	86.92	67.96
do not know	0.42	0.00	3.74	10.68
Total	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00

Source: Own elaboration based on DignityFIRM survey.

Note: sample constrained to firms employing migrants

The results obtained for firms which employ migrants may be compared with the results obtained for firms that do not have such employees. Interestingly, in this case, apart from the Netherlands, the shares of firms admitting to not fully compliant employment are much lower (Table 12) and vary from 5% for Italy, 7% for Poland to 11% for Spain. Interestingly, in the Netherlands, the distribution does not differ significantly from the distribution for firms which employ migrants.

Table 12. Share of firms employing “before formalities are fulfilled”, by country (in percent) – firms not employing migrants

	Country			
	Italy	Netherlands	Poland	Spain
yes	4.84	10.91	4.08	6.32
no	95.16	87.88	92.86	88.42
do not know	0.00	1.21	3.06	5.26
Total	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00

Source: Own elaboration based on DignityFIRM survey.

Note: sample constrained to firms not employing migrants

Overall, when judging by the responses to the questions presented above, one may assess the scale of non-compliant employment in general to vary between countries, with higher instances in Spain and Italy (up to 30%) and lower in Poland and the Netherlands (around 10%) in the case of foreigners (or firms which employ foreigners). For firms which employ nationals only, the reported extent of non-compliance seems to be much lower.

5.3.1. List experiment: scale of informal employment of foreigners

The results based on the “traditional” part of the questionnaire may be compared with the results of a list experiment. In this case, as mentioned above, the respondents were randomly divided into two test groups and a control group, which were presented with different lists. Each respondent was supposed to indicate how many elements of the list were true in relation to their firm. The control group list consisted of 5 items, all related to employment of workers, with some elements having a positive aspect (bonuses, investments), while some elements having a negative light (delays in payment, accident, not taking holidays):

- a) Some employees did not receive their remuneration on time
- b) An employee had an accident at work
- c) Some employees’ holidays were not taken
- d) Employees were paid bonuses
- e) The company invested in new machines or equipment for workers.

The respondents in the test groups were presented with lists extended by an element of:

- f) A native employee was hired without fulfilling all formalities

or

g) A foreigner was hired without fulfilling all formalities

In such a setting, one may assume that when comparing the group averages of the responses, the differences between the averages of the test groups and control group may be interpreted as the share of firms that employ a foreigner/native without fulfilling all formalities. The presumption is that when respondents are asked to indicate only the number of elements on the list, rather than whether any particular element is true, they will be more truthful in their responses and the derived scale of informal employment will reflect the true rate better than when measure by direct questions.

Tables 13-14 present the results, separately for firms that employ foreigners and firms which do not. **For Poland**, the results are consistent with the results of direct questions, but show a much larger share of informality: approximately 31% (= 1.97-1.66) of firms which employ foreigners are involved in informal employment of migrants. The results for the informal employment of natives in this case are similar. **For Spain**, the scale of informality may be assessed as almost 50% (2.36-1.88) in the case of employment of foreigners, and much less for nationals. The pattern is therefore consistent with that inferred from the traditional questions, albeit the shares are higher than in direct responses.

Table 13. Average number of elements on list, by country

	Country			
	Italy	Netherlands	Poland	Spain
Test group 1 (national)	2.04	1.49	2.22	2.12
Test group 2 (foreigner)	2.06	1.51	1.97	2.36
Control group	2.01	1.68	1.66	1.88

Source: Own elaboration based on DignityFIRM survey.

Note: sample constrained to firms employing migrants

Table 14. Average number of elements on list, by country

	Country			
	Italy	Netherlands	Poland	Spain
Test group 1 (national)	1.77	1.36	1.92	1.48
Control group	1.35	1.44	1.60	1.36

Source: Own elaboration based on DignityFIRM survey.

Note: sample constrained to firms not employing migrants

Interestingly, **for Italy**, no informality among firms employing migrants is observed. However, a significant proportion of informality is observed in firms which employ nationals only. On the other hand, **for the Netherlands**, an unintuitive outcome is observed: among firms which saw longer lists of elements, the average number of responses were lower than among firms, which saw shorter lists of elements. This indicates that when seeing a disturbing element on the list, respondents had a tendency to indicate a lower number, so that nobody suspects they had been involved in informal employment.

Overall, the results of the list experiment are affected by the fact that the samples are not large and therefore the differences in the shares may not be significant and are prone to distortion. However, what is more important is that the experimental approach does not allow to overcome the barrier of lack of trust with respect to the interviewer in specific countries (cultures).

5.3.2 Vignette experiment: preferences towards informal employment of foreigners

Apart from questions related to actual employment, respondents also faced a discrete choice experiment, in which they were asked to choose a preferred option from two presented. As mentioned above, the options differed in terms of the nationality of a potential employee, the formality of employment, the wage level as well as duration of contract and potential fine for irregular employment. Please note that this report only presents and interprets the basic outcomes. More in-depth results require econometric modelling (which will be the next analytical step).

When presented with a choice between a migrant employee and a native employee, in approximately 40% choice situations respondents chose the native employee (Table 15). In the sample, we may observe higher propensity to choose natives for those who declared they are primarily looking for natives and lower for those who declared they look for foreigners, but what must be noted is that in the (dominating) group of respondents who declare they do not take nationality into account, the share of choice situations where a native was chosen is significantly lower than 50%.

Table 15. Average share of choice options when native chosen over foreigner, by country and declared hiring strategy (in percent)

	Country			
	Italy	Netherlands	Poland	Spain
Primarily looking for natives	46.71	51.17	48.81	50.59
Primarily looking for foreigners	30.26	*	*	23.48
Nationality not important	39.62	43.29	43.22	39.06
Overall	41.06	44.91	46.17	43.85

Source: Own elaboration based on DignityFIRM survey.

Note: * Value suppressed due to small sample size

As far as preference with respect to legality is concerned, the respondents showed a clear propensity for regular forms of employment, with 92% such indications for the Netherlands, but slightly lower rates of 87% for Italy, 83% for Poland and 81% for Spain (Table 16).

Table 16. Average share of choice options when regular employment chosen over informal, by country (in percent) and response to morality questions

	Country			
	Italy	Netherlands	Poland	Spain
Overall	87	92	83	81
Claiming state benefits which you are not entitled to				
“Is never justified”	90	92	84	80
Other than “is never justified”	80	88	80	80
Cheating on tax if you have the chance				
“Is never justified”	87	92	83	79
Other than “is never justified”	87	90	75	86

Source: Own elaboration based on DignityFIRM survey.

When tabulating the preferences for regular employment against responses to questions related to morality, one may observe a lower propensity to choose the irregular form for respondents who declared that in their view, behaviours such as claiming state benefits when one is not entitled to or cheating on tax if one has the chance are never justified, than respondents who were not as rigorous in this respect for the Netherlands and Poland. For Italy, the results were not as evident, as the tax evasion dimension did not differentiate the respondents’ choices. For Spain, the results were contradictory, as they did not differ with respect to the state benefits claiming question and went in a non-intuitive direction for the tax evasion question (Table 16).

6. LIMITATIONS OF THE STUDY

This report presents the results of a survey that aimed to analyse both formal and informal employment in selected sectors of the economy. The methodology was designed with this aim in mind, but when analysing the data, it is important to consider that both the survey design and implementation have several limitations. In particular, these may stem from the fact that:

- The representativeness of the sampling frame (the D&B database) is uncertain;
- There may be biases in the sample structure due to high numbers of non-responses, particularly in Poland.
- The form of the survey (telephone interview) may not ensure trust among respondents, which could lead to them concealing their true preferences and the prevalence of undesirable behaviour (e.g. non-compliant forms of employment).
- The survey was conducted by different teams in the four studied countries, which does not allow for full comparability of results. The duration of interviews varied significantly between countries (they were much shorter in Poland and the Netherlands than in Italy and Spain; see data in Appendix A3). The short duration of some interviews suggests that employers' responses to questions, especially the experimental ones, might not be as reliable as those in questionnaires that took longer to complete.
- Although the research team worked hard to ensure the questions were fully comparable between countries, some language and contextual nuances could not be avoided.
- Sample sizes are not large enough to allow meaningful disaggregation of some results by country and sector in cases where less common outputs are concerned, or where having or not having experience of hiring a migrant might differentiate the studied population even further.
- The experimental questions posed some difficulties to respondents. First of all, they were presented by telephone (which might hinder clarity) and second, they might have been considered by some respondents as unnatural.

7. CONCLUDING REMARKS

Empirical research on migration is usually subject to a high risk of bias, and this is particularly true of specific studies such as those carried out in the DignityFIRM project. A good example is the study covered by this report. It focused on entrepreneurs in specific sectors of the economy and, in addition, on people who had to have specific knowledge of recruitment and employment processes. Moreover, it largely concerned a difficult and sensitive area: informal employment. This makes the reservations outlined in the previous section all the more important. When analysing the results, it is important to acknowledge the limitations of the research material obtained, which include potential imperfections in the sampling procedure (a common concern in the context of business surveys) and variations in the survey's execution across individual countries. Additionally, there are specific instances where interviewers encountered difficulties in acquiring detailed and often sensitive information regarding informal employment situations, which can be perceived as sensitive due to its potential impact on the individuals concerned.

The present summary was initiated with a reiteration of the risks and limitations, with the objective of emphasising that, despite the numerous risks, the research material obtained provides information of considerable interest.

Firstly, while the analysed sectors are in fairly good economic and financial condition, they are still coping with the economic effects of the pandemic. The level of automation is low/very low (especially outside of the food processing sector), which is important in the context of the analysed processes, as labour costs and access to workers have been identified as significant barriers to development. At the same time, there are significant differences between individual countries. These differences stem from the initial assumptions (a comparison of countries representing different dimensions of welfare capitalism and diverse economic structures) and confirm the ongoing disparities within the EU.

Secondly, the scale of foreign employment in the F2F sector varies greatly depending on the country: it is relatively large in Poland and the Netherlands, and very large in Italy and Spain. Other aspects of this phenomenon vary greatly depending on the context. In Poland, for example, it mainly concerned Ukrainian citizens; in Italy and Spain, it mainly referred to migrants from Africa, South America and Romania; and in the Netherlands, it mainly concerned migrants from Central and Eastern European countries. Notably, migrant skill levels also varied considerably, and the primary incentive for employing migrants was to reduce costs amid mounting challenges in recruiting local workers. At least at the declarative level, employers did not differentiate between hiring foreign and domestic workers.

Thirdly, analysing informal employment poses a much greater challenge and will be the focus of future work (see below). However, even based on direct questions, it can be concluded that

informal employment is widespread: when asked about employment before all formalities had been completed, 10% (Poland) to 32% (Italy) of companies employing immigrants indicated this (and generally, these percentages were higher than for companies not employing foreigners). These results are confirmed by experimental studies, although additional tests will be necessary in this case.

Finally, it should be emphasised that this report was primarily technical in nature, i.e. its purpose was to provide a relatively detailed description of the process of preparing and conducting the survey. The results and conclusions contained therein should be regarded as preliminary, and as an initial point of departure for further analysis. These analyses will be multidirectional. Firstly, econometric methodologies will be employed to identify the fundamental mechanisms and strategies underpinning formal and informal employment of foreigners, with particular emphasis on the experimental dimension of the study. Secondly, the quantitative data analysed in this report will be used in conjunction with a substantial qualitative material, in the hope that the use of mixed methods will allow for a more complete understanding of the phenomenon of informal employment in the F2F sectors in Europe.

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APPENDIX

A1: SURVEY QUESTIONNAIRE

INTRODUCTION

Q0. Good morning, my name is I am an Interviewer in the DignityFirm project financed by the European Union, we are currently conducting a research study on hiring foreign workers in the Food-to-Fork sector. Please tell me, in which sector does your company operate?

1. Agriculture and fishing (excluding tobacco cultivation)
2. Food processing (excluding feed and pet food production)
3. Gastronomy
4. Other -> end of interview

Q1. I would like to ask you to connect me with a person who decides about hiring employees in your company: the owner, president, director or head of the human resources department. If there are several such persons, please connect me with the one who has a relatively longest tenure at your company.

[After obtaining a connection with a potential respondent:]

Q2a. Good morning, my name is I am an Interviewer..... We are currently conducting a scientific survey on hiring foreign workers within the DignityFirm project financed by the European Union. The survey is completely anonymous. The interview will take approximately 15 minutes. Would you agree to participate in the survey?

1. yes
2. no -> end of interview

[If Q2a = 1 (yes)]

Q2b. Thank you. I would like to inform you that the obtained data will be presented only in the form of aggregated statistics, and anonymous data will be securely stored for 10 years. Participation in the study is voluntary, and you can opt out at any time. If you would like to learn more about the project or the privacy policy, I can provide or send a link to the project website. Would you like to receive additional information about the project?

1. Yes
2. No -> proceed to question Q3

[If Q2b = 1 (yes)]

Q2c. Would you like to note down the website address or provide me with an email address to receive the appropriate link?

[provide the link or note the company's email address]

[If Q2b = 1 (yes)]

Q2d. Would you like to participate in the survey now or after reviewing the provided information?

1. Now -> continue the interview -> proceed to question Q3
2. Later; when? Schedule the next contact date

Q3. What is your position in the company?

1. owner
2. president
3. director
4. human resources manager
5. other position (provided that it is a person responsible for hiring employees or who has knowledge of the process, and the person who manages the company cannot take part in the survey) - what position?
6. other -> end of interview

Q4. How many employees in total – foreigners and [native workers] – worked at your company on any terms at the peak of high season in 2024? By work, we also mean a situation in which the employee is formally employed by another entity (such as a temporary employment agency) or self-employed.

ANS : [_____]

0 -> end of interview.

>49 -> end of interview

EMPLOYMENT OF FOREIGNERS AND NATIVE WORKERS

Q5. Has at least one foreigner worked at your company for any period of time, on any terms, in 2024? By “foreigner” we mean a person who does not have [xxx] citizenship. By work, we also mean a situation in which the employee is formally employed by another entity (such as a temporary employment agency) or self-employed. [Interviewer: If the company has been operating for a shorter period - since the beginning of operations. If the respondent does not have knowledge of the entire period, let them refer to the knowledge they have].

1. yes
2. no

[If Q5 = 1 (yes)]

Q6. How many foreigners worked at your company, on any terms, at the peak of high season in 2024?

[_____]persons

[If Q5 = 1 (yes)]

Q7. Can you estimate how many of these foreigners were women?

Q7A: [_____] persons

OR, if the respondent finds it difficult to provide the number of people in absolute terms
Q7B: % of the number of people

Q8. Do you anticipate that in 2025 your company will hire a foreigner, on any terms, even for a short time? Please indicate the most appropriate answer.

[Interviewer: read the options]

1. you plan to hire a foreigner
2. you do not plan to hire a foreigner, but it is probable
3. you do not plan to hire a foreigner and it is unlikely.

[If Q5 = 1 (yes)]

Q9. Foreigners from which countries worked at your company in 2024? [LIST – multiple choice, max 5 choices]

[If Q5 = 1 (yes)]

Q10A. In what types of positions were native workers and foreigners employed at your company in 2024? Please indicate all groups of positions.

[Interviewer: read the options]

	Native workers	Foreigners
1. Management	Yes / No	Yes / No
2. Office work	Yes / No	Yes / No
3. Skilled manual	Yes / No	Yes / No
4. Unskilled manual	Yes / No	Yes / No

[If Q5 = 2 (no)]

Q10A. In what types of positions were native workers employed at your company in 2024? Please indicate all groups of positions.

[Interviewer: read the options]

	Native workers
1. Management	Yes / No
2. Office work	Yes / No
3. Skilled manual	Yes / No

4. Unskilled manual	Yes / No
---------------------	----------

[If Q5 = 1 (yes) AND at least one “yes” option was selected in the Native workers column in Q10A]

Q11A. What type of employment and working hours did the employees in your company have in 2024? Please indicate all categories, separately for native workers and foreigners.

	Native workers	Foreigners
1. Permanent jobs	Yes / No	Yes / No
2. Seasonal/casual work	Yes / No	Yes / No
3. Full-time	Yes / No	Yes / No
4. Part-time	Yes / No	Yes / No
5. Standard working hours	Yes / No	Yes / No
6. Non-standard working hours (evenings/nights/weekends/holidays)	Yes / No	Yes / No
7. Self-employment	Yes/No	Yes/No
8. Employment through temporary employment agencies	Yes/No	Yes/No

[If Q5 = 1 (yes) AND no “yes” options were selected in the Native workers column in Q10A]

Q11B. What type of employment and working hours did the employees in your company have in 2024? Please indicate all categories for foreigners.

	Foreigners
1. Permanent jobs	Yes / No
2. Seasonal/casual work	Yes / No
3. Full-time	Yes / No
4. Part-time	Yes / No
5. Standard working hours	Yes / No

6. Non-standard working hours (evenings/nights/weekends/holidays)	Yes / No
7. Self-employment	Yes/No
8. Employment through temporary employment agencies	Yes/No

[If Q5 = 2 (no)]

Q11C. What type of employment and working hours did the employees in your company have in 2024? Please indicate all categories for native workers.

	Native workers
1. Permanent jobs	Yes / No
2. Seasonal/casual work	Yes / No
3. Full-time	Yes / No
4. Part-time	Yes / No
5. Standard working hours	Yes / No
6. Non-standard working hours (evenings/nights/weekends/holidays)	Yes / No
7. Self-employment	Yes/No
8. Employment through temporary employment agencies	Yes/No

[If Q5 = 1 (yes)]

Q12. On the basis of what documents did the foreigners employed in your company work in 2024? Please indicate all those used.

01. work permit

02. seasonal work permit

03. contract of service or intra-group posting for posted workers

- 04. student visa or family-based permit
- 05. refugee status and temporary protection status, including asylum or the status of Ukrainian war migrants
- 06. documents of EU-citizens
- 07. employer's statement on entrusting work to a foreigner [Poland]
- 09. long-term residence permit [ITALY]
- 08. other

[If Q5 = 1 (yes) AND at least one "yes" option was selected in the Native workers column in Q10A]

Q13. Please compare the average labor costs of a foreigner and [native employees], working in your company in positions of the same type, in 2024 [The interviewer is shown the job groups from the Job Classification indicated simultaneously in question 10] For jobs: JOB GROUP NAME

[If the "Management" row in question Q10A has both the "Native worker" option marked as "YES" and the "Foreigners" option marked as "YES":]

Q13.1 For management

- a) labor costs of a foreigner were higher than for native workers
- b) the foreigners' labor costs were the same as for native workers
- c) labor costs of a foreigner were lower than for native workers

[If the "Office work" row in question Q10A has both the "Native worker" option marked as "YES" and the "Foreigners" option marked as "YES":]

Q13.2 For office workers

- a) labor costs of a foreigner were higher than for native workers
- b) the foreigners' labor costs were the same as for native workers
- c) labor costs of a foreigner were lower than for native workers

[If the "Skilled manual" row in question Q10A has both the "Native worker" option marked as "YES" and the "Foreigners" option marked as "YES":]

Q13.3 For skilled manual workers

- a) labor costs of a foreigner were higher than for native workers
- b) the foreigners' labor costs were the same as for native workers
- c) labor costs of a foreigner were lower than for native workers

[If the "Unskilled manual" row in question Q10A has both the "Native worker" option marked as "YES" and the "Foreigners" option marked as "YES":]

Q13.4 For unskilled manual

- a) labor costs of a foreigner were higher than for native workers
- b) the foreigners' labor costs were the same as for native workers
- c) labor costs of a foreigner were lower than for native workers

[If Q5 = 1 (yes) AND at least one "yes" option was selected in the Native workers column in Q10A]

Q14A. How does your company recruit employees? Please indicate all methods used, separately for native workers and foreigners:

	Native workers	Foreigners
1. External recruitment company	Yes / No	Yes / No
2. Internal recruitment unit	Yes / No	Yes / No
3. Mass media and social media	Yes / No	Yes / No
4. Job centers/public employment agencies	Yes / No	Yes / No
5. Temporary employment agencies	Yes / No	Yes / No
6. Informal labor exchanges	Yes / No	Yes / No
7. Other means - what kind?		

[If Q5 = 1 (yes) AND no “yes” options were selected in the Native workers column in Q10A]

Q14B. How does your company recruit employees? Please indicate all methods used, for foreigners:

	Foreigners
1. External recruitment company	Yes / No
2. Internal recruitment unit	Yes / No
3. Mass media and social media	Yes / No
4. Job centers/public employment agencies	Yes / No
5. Temporary employment agencies	Yes / No
6. Informal labor exchanges	Yes / No
7. Other means - what kind?	

[If Q5 = 2 (no)]

Q14C. How does your company recruit employees? Please indicate all methods used for native workers:

	Native workers
1. External recruitment company	Yes / No
2. Internal recruitment unit	Yes / No
3. Mass media and social media	Yes / No
4. Job centers/public employment agencies	Yes / No
5. Temporary employment agencies	Yes / No
6. Informal labor exchanges	Yes / No
7. Other means - what kind?	

EXPERIMENTS

LIST EXPERIMENT (randomized between respondents!)

Q15A. If option 1 was selected in question Q5 AND at least one "YES" option was selected in the "native workers" column in question Q10A, the respondent is asked a randomly selected question from a pool of THREE questions: Q15.1, Q15.2, Q15.3.

Q15B. If option 1 was selected in question Q5 AND no "YES" option was selected in the "Poles" column in question Q10A, the respondent is asked a randomly selected question from a pool of TWO questions: Q15.2, Q15.3.

Q15C. If option 2 was selected in question Q5, the respondent is asked a randomly selected question from a pool of TWO questions: Q15.1, Q15.3.

Q15.1 Now I will read six statements. Please count how many of them were true regarding your company in 2024. At the end, I will ask you about this number. Please remember, we are not asking which ones are true, just how many of them are.

- a) Some employees did not receive their remuneration on time

- b) An employee had an accident at work
- c) Some employees' holidays were not taken
- d) Employees were paid bonuses
- e) The company invested in new machines or equipment for workers.
- f) A native employee was hired without fulfilling all formalities

Please indicate HOW MANY occurred in your company in 2024?

Q15.2 Now I will read six statements. Please count how many of them were true regarding your company in 2024. At the end, I will ask you about this number. Please remember, we are not asking which ones are true, just how many of them are.

- a) Some employees did not receive their remuneration on time
- b) An employee had an accident at work
- c) Some employees' holidays were not taken
- d) Employees were paid bonuses
- e) The company invested in new machines or equipment for workers.
- f) A foreigner was hired without fulfilling all formalities

Please indicate HOW MANY occurred in your company in 2024?.....

Q15.3 Now I will read five statements. Please count how many of them were true regarding your company in 2024. At the end, I will ask you about this number. Please remember, we are not asking which ones are true, just how many of them are.

- a) Some employees did not receive their remuneration on time
- b) An employee had an accident at work
- c) Some employees' holidays were not taken
- d) Employees were paid bonuses
- e) The company invested in new machines or equipment for workers.

Please indicate HOW MANY occurred in your company in 2024?.....

CONTINGENT CHOICE (randomized between respondents!)

Respondents are asked a randomly selected block of 4 questions from the pool of blocks Q16-Q19, depending on the economic sector indicated in question 0 (i.e., a different pool for respondents who selected option a) agriculture in question 0, a different pool for respondents who selected option b) processing, and a different pool for respondents who selected option c) gastronomy).

TABULAR VERSION:

Q16W. Assume that you are hiring a new worker. Usually, there is more than one form of employment possible and more than one potential type of worker. Please specify, which of these (two) options you would choose? You may assume that the available options (workers) would be equivalent in all dimensions not mentioned below.

Type of employee	Native	EU/non-EU foreigner
1. Formal employment	Yes	NO
2. Type of contract	permanent	temporary
3. Hourly wage accepted	... EUR	... EUR
4. Possible fine for irregular employment EUR EUR

a)

b)

TELEPHONE VERSION:

Q16T. Assume that you are hiring a new worker. Usually, there is more than one form of employment possible and more than one potential type of worker. I will now read descriptions of two options. Please specify, which of these options you would choose? You may assume that the available options (workers) would be equivalent in all dimensions not mentioned.

Option 1: A native worker, formally employed on a permanent contract, who accepts a salary of ... EUR per hour.

Option 2: A foreigner from the EU, employed informally on a temporary contract, who accepts a salary of ... EUR per hour, in a situation where a financial penalty for irregular employment would be ... EUR.

Q17. CONTINGENT CHOICE 2

Q18. CONTINGENT CHOICE 3

Q19. CONTINGENT CHOICE 4

ATTITUDE TOWARDS FOREIGNERS

Q20. Assume that your company is hiring a new worker. Some employers take workers' citizenship into consideration, and some don't. Please indicate the most accurate statement for your company:

1. we are primarily looking for native workers as employees.
2. we are primarily looking for foreigners as employees
3. when looking for employees, we do not consider whether the candidates are native workers or foreigners

Q21. In your opinion, what would be the reasons for employing foreign workers instead of native workers in your company? Please indicate all applicable answers:

[Interviewer: read options]

01. not enough native workers apply for the job
02. foreigners accept lower wages
03. foreigners accept employment in more flexible forms
04. foreigners work better
05. foreigners have specific qualifications required for the job (e.g. languages, intercultural competences, professional contacts, locally unavailable skills)
07. majority of applications are foreign
08. other – please specify: (OPEN)

Mark only if none of the above options are chosen:

09. there are no special reasons for employing foreigners

Q22. What, in your opinion, speaks against employing foreigners in your company? Please indicate up all applicable answers:

[Interviewer: read all options]

01. language difficulties in communicating between foreigners and [native workers]
02. cultural differences
03. the time it takes to obtain documentation to employ a foreigner
04. the costs of obtaining documentation to employ a foreigner
05. foreigners have higher salary expectations
06. difficulties in using/adapting competencies acquired in another country
07. native workers do not want to work with foreigners
08. bad experience with foreign workers in the past
09. difficulties in finding housing for foreigners
10. language communication problems with customers
11. other – please specify: (OPEN)

Mark only if none of the above options are chosen:

12. there are no special reasons against hiring foreigners

[If Q5 = 1 (yes)]

Q23. Do the foreign employees of your organization have health insurance in [country]?

[Interviewer: read options]

1. yes, all of them
2. yes, some of them

3. no, they do not, but an appropriate procedure is under way
4. no, they do not
5. I don't know [do not read]

ATTITUDES TOWARDS TAXES

Q24. I will now read two statements. Please indicate where you would place your opinion about the following behaviors on a scale from 1 to 5, where 1 means the behavior can never be justified, and 5 means the behavior can always be justified:

- a) Claiming state benefits which you are not entitled to
- 1 (the behavior can never be justified)
 - 2 (it should not be justified, but in certain cases, it may be)
 - 3 (it can sometimes be justified, and sometimes not)
 - 4 (it should be justified, but in certain cases, it should not)
 - 5 (the behavior can always be justified)

- b) Cheating on tax if you have the chance
- 1 (the behavior can never be justified)
 - 2 (it should not be justified, but in certain cases, it may be)
 - 3 (it can sometimes be justified, and sometimes not)
 - 4 (it should be justified, but in certain cases, it should not)
 - 5 (the behavior can always be justified)

Q25. Please tell me for each item listed how much confidence you have in them:

- a) The social security system (a great deal/ quite a lot / not very much / none at all)
- b) The justice system (a great deal/ quite a lot / not very much / none at all)
- c) The government (a great deal/ quite a lot / not very much / none at all)

FUNCTIONING OF THE COMPANY

Q26. Has your company's turnover in 2024 increased, decreased or remained the same with respect to 2023?

1. increased
2. remained at the same level
3. decreased
4. do not know [do not read]

Q27. Does your company currently face any obstacles to doing

business? Please indicate all important barriers:

01. low demand
02. taxes/regulations
03. inflation/cost of raw materials
04. lack of human resources
05. labor costs
06. high competition
07. other – please specify (OPEN)

Mark only if none of the above were chosen

08. lack of barriers

Q28. Does your company have valid long-term contracts that affect the scale of its business?
(e.g., a product supply contract for a warehouse)

1. yes
2. no
3. do not know [do not read]

Q29. Has the number of vacancies in your company changed in 2024 relative to 2023,
disregarding seasonal fluctuations?

[Interviewer: read options]

1. increased
2. remained the same
3. decreased

Q30. Did it happen in your company in 2024 that at peak season or in other moments where quick
help was needed, a new employee started working before all formalities were fulfilled?

1. yes
2. no
3. do not know [do not read]

Q31T. I will now read several statements. Please indicate which of them occurred in your company
in the last three years (2022-2024):

1. The company changed its name or organizational structure
2. The company changed its business profile
3. The company was subject to a food safety inspection (seed control, sanitary inspection, etc.)
4. The company was inspected by any institutions related to the legality of employment
5. The company significantly increased its scale of operations or the size of its workforce
6. The company introduced technological innovations enabling work automation

Q31W. Below you will find several statements. Please indicate which

of them occurred in your company in the last three years (2022-2024):

1. The company changed its name or organizational structure
2. The company changed its business profile
3. The company was subject to a food safety inspection (seed control, sanitary inspection, etc.)
4. The company was inspected by any institutions related to the legality of employment
5. The company significantly increased its scale of operations or the size of its workforce
6. The company introduced technological innovations enabling work automation

That was the last question of the survey. Thank you for your time.

A2: STRUCTURE OF THE SAMPLING FRAME

1. POLAND

Table A1. Records purchased for the survey in Poland, by sector

Sectors	Total
Agriculture	3746
Food processing	3761
Food service	4215
Total	11722

Source: Own elaboration based on information provided by the surveying company.

Table A2. Employment structure in the purchased database for the survey in Poland, by sector

Number of employees	Agriculture	Food Processing	Food service	Total
1	27	25	31	83
2 - 4	746	1179	1560	3485
5 - 9	2318	1265	2119	5702
10 - 19	587	658	442	1687
20 - 29	35	381	46	462
30 - 39	19	153	11	183
40 - 49	14	100	6	120
Total	3746	3761	4215	11722

Source: Own elaboration based on information provided by the surveying company.

2. THE NETHERLANDS

Table A3. Records purchased for the survey in the Netherlands, by sector

Sectors	Total
Agriculture	800
Food processing	1200
Food service	900
Total	2900

Source: Own elaboration based on information provided by the surveying company.

Table A4. Employment structure in the purchased database for the survey in the Netherlands, by sector

Number of employees	Agriculture	Food Processing	Food service	Total
1	54	116	85	255
2-4	92	150	147	389
5-9	169	182	149	500
10-19	176	217	156	549
20-29	153	234	161	548
30-39	94	178	127	399
40-49	62	123	75	260
Total	800	1200	900	2900

Source: Own elaboration based on information provided by the surveying company.

3. ITALY

Table A5. Records purchased for the survey in Italy, by sector

Sectors	Total
Agriculture	900
Food processing	800
Food service	1000
Total	2700

Source: Own elaboration based on information provided by the surveying company.

Table A6. Employment structure in the purchased database for the survey in Italy, by sector

Number of employees	Agriculture	Food Processing	Food service	Total
1	48	37	35	120
2-4	69	92	107	268
5-9	112	102	340	554
10-19	145	111	164	420
20-29	158	135	149	442
30-39	191	151	104	446
40-49	177	172	101	450
Total	900	800	1000	2700

Source: Own elaboration based on information provided by the surveying company.

4. SPAIN

Table A7. Records purchased for the survey in Spain, by sector

Sectors	Total
Agriculture	1000
Food processing	1200
Food service	1100
Total	3300

Source: Own elaboration based on information provided by the surveying company.

Table A8. Employment structure in the purchased database for the survey in Spain, by sector

Number of employees	Agriculture	Food Processing	Food service	Total
1	88	79	71	238
2-4	201	96	73	370
5-9	238	217	166	621
10-19	223	329	319	871
20-29	122	216	227	565
30-39	73	139	148	360
40-49	55	124	96	275
Total	1000	1200	1100	3300

Source: Own elaboration based on information provided by the surveying company.

A3: SURVEY IMPLEMENTATION – TECHNICAL DETAILS

1. POLAND

Table A9. Average duration of interviews in Poland

	Average
Average time if firm employs foreigners, n=106	0:14:89
Average time if firm does not employ foreigners, n=194	0:12:27
Average time overall	0:13:20

Source: Own elaboration based on information provided by the surveying company.

Table A10. Median interview duration in Poland

	Median
Median for Agriculture	0:13:55
Median for Food processing	0:12:20
Median for Food service	0:12:02
Overall median	0:12:55

Source: Own elaboration based on information provided by the surveying company.

Table A11. Distribution of interviews by day in Poland

	Number of interviews
March 20	8
March 21	8
March 24	17
March 25	17
March 26	20
March 27	10
March 28	25
March 31	23
April 1	22
April 2	20
April 3	18
April 4	18
April 7	9
April 8	20
April 9	7
April 10	5
April 11	5
April 14	12
April 15	4
April 16	13
April 17	3
April 22	3
April 23	8
April 24	5

Source: Own elaboration based on information provided by the surveying company.

Table A12. Geographical sample structure by sector and employment size class in Poland

Sector	Agriculture			Food Processing			Food service			
	1-9	10-29	30-49	1-9	10-29	30-49	1-9	10-29	30-49	
Province										
Lower Silesia	4	3	2	0	4	2	4	3	0	22
Kujawsko-Pomorskie	5	7	1	2	7	0	1	1	1	25
Lodzkie	0	1	1	1	3	2	3	4	0	15
Lubelskie	2	4	2	1	2	2	4	2	0	19
Lubuskie	0	0	1	2	1	0	1	0	1	6
Malopolskie	1	0	0	5	7	1	5	9	1	29
Mazovia	2	3	0	2	6	4	5	8	3	33
Opolskie	5	4	0	2	2	1	1	1	0	16
Podkarpackie	2	0	0	2	5	1	1	2	0	13
Podlaskie	2	0	1	0	2	2	0	3	0	10
Pomeranian	3	2	2	0	3	0	2	2	0	14
Silesia	2	2	1	6	4	4	6	4	1	30
Swietokrzyskie	0	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	6
Warminsko-Mazurskie	2	3	3	2	1	1	0	3	1	16
Greater Poland	4	3	1	4	6	2	5	3	1	29
West Pomeranian	3	4	2	1	1	0	3	2	1	17
Overall	37	36	18	31	55	23	42	48	10	

Source: Own elaboration based on information provided by the surveying company.

Table A13. Database records by effect of contact in Poland

Records not contacted:	Overall	Agriculture	Food Processing	Food service
busy	714	291	218	205
no answer	2091	714	590	787
connection unsuccessful	548	112	115	321
voice mail/answering machine	978	292	235	451
there is no such number	1196	423	331	442
fax	36	10	13	13
	5563	1842	1502	2219
Records contacted:				
Completed interviews, which were included in the final database	300	91	109	100
Completed interviews that were rejected as a result of quality control	6	1	2	3
Does not meet the criteria (sector)	811	420	139	252
Refusal to participate in the study - lack of confidence	415	115	162	138
Refusal to participate in the study - lack of time	1291	365	400	526
Refusal to participate in the study - fear of data privacy	37	14	14	9
Refusal to participate in the study - refusal to give a reason	1940	543	737	660
Appointments	363	95	143	125
CAWI survey request	228	53	92	83
Started and not completed - interrupted during the interview (lack of time/length of survey)	157	51	54	52
Wrong number	611	170	141	300
	6159	1918	1993	2248

Source: Own elaboration based on information provided by the surveying company.

2. THE NETHERLANDS

Table A14. Median interview duration in the Netherlands

	Median
Median for Agriculture	10.59
Median for Food processing	10.64
Median for Food service	10.93
Overall median	10.74

Source: Own elaboration based on information provided by the surveying company.

Table A15. Average duration of interviews in the Netherlands

	Average
Average time if firm employs foreigners, n=135	13.26
Average time if firm does not employ foreigners, n=169	10.80
Average time overall	11.90

Source: Own elaboration based on information provided by the surveying company.

Table A16. Distribution of interviews by day in the Netherlands

	Number of interviews
April 14	3
April 15	11
April 16	14
April 17	1
April 23	10
April 24	4
April 25	1
April 28	10
April 29	11
April 30	13
May 1	9
May 2	12
May 3	1
May 5	6
May 6	15
May 7	19
May 8	18

May 9	13
May 12	32
May 13	24
May 14	20
May 15	22
May 16	25
May 17	6
May 19	4

Source: Own elaboration based on information provided by the surveying company.

Table A17. Geographical sample structure by sector and employment size class in the Netherlands

Sector	Agriculture			Food Processing			Food service			
	1-9	10-29	30-49	1-9	10-29	30-49	1-9	10-29	30-49	
Region										
East	12	11	3	6	4	3	12	8	6	65
North	3	2	1	3	7	3	5	5	2	31
Randstad (Amsterdam/ Rotterdam/ the Hague)	1	5	5	6	5	1	5	9	1	38
South	13	14	8	10	5	4	11	10	6	81
West	13	6	13	9	10	4	13	16	5	89
	42	38	30	34	31	15	46	48	20	

Source: Own elaboration based on information provided by the surveying company.

Table A18. Database records by effect of contact in the Netherlands

Records not contacted:	
busy	228
no answer	905
voice mail/answering machine	93
	1226
Records contacted:	
Completed interviews, included in the final database	304

Completed interviews that were rejected as a result of quality control	3
Does not meet the criteria (sector)	306
Refusal to participate in the study	517
Appointments	460
CAWI survey request	84
	1674

Source: Own elaboration based on information provided by the surveying company.

3. ITALY

Table A19. Average duration of interviews in Italy

	Average
Average time if firm employs foreigners, n=238	26,62
Average time if firm does not employ foreigners, n=62	23,20
Average time overall	25.92

Source: Own elaboration based on information provided by the surveying company.

Table A20. Median interview duration in Italy

	Median
Median for Agriculture	17.35
Median for Food processing	31.34
Median for Food service	34.08
Overall median	24.18

Source: Own elaboration based on information provided by the surveying company.

Table A21. Distribution of interviews by day in Italy

	Number of interviews
April 11	4
April 12	4
April 13	2
April 14	11
April 15	7
April 16	2
April 17	9
April 18	3

April 22	8
April 23	8
April 24	10
April 25	3
April 26	4
April 27	1
April 28	13
April 29	17
April 30	13
May 2	18
May 3	8
May 4	4
May 5	19
May 6	27
May 7	24
May 8	33
May 9	41
May 10	2
May 12	4
May 13	1

Source: Own elaboration based on information provided by the surveying company.

Table A22. Geographical sample structure by sector and employment size class in Italy

Sector	Agriculture			Food Processing			Food service			
	1-9	10-29	30-49	1-9	10-29	30-49	1-9	10-29	30-49	
Region										
Abruzzo	0	0	0	1	0	0	1	0	0	2
Basilicata	1	1	1	2	1	1	1	3	1	12
Calabria	1	0	0	1	2	0	1	1	1	7
Campania	6	8	3	3	9	1	8	4	0	42
Emilia-Romagna	0	1	0	1	2	0	2	1	0	7
Friuli-Venezia Giulia	3	2	0	2	0	0	1	4	1	13
Lazio	1	10	2	4	4	2	6	4	4	37
Liguria	0	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	2
Lombardy	4	8	4	8	13	7	6	11	2	63
Marche	0	2	0	1	1	0	1	1	0	6
Molise	1	2	0	2	0	0	1	2	1	9
Piemonte	1	1	1	1	2	0	1	2	0	9
Puglia	1	2	0	0	0	0	0	2	1	6
Sardegna	0	1	0	2	1	1	1	1	0	7
Sicilia	4	6	5	3	7	4	6	7	3	45
Toscana	2	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	3
Trentino-Alto Adige	1	1	0	0	1	1	1	0	1	6
Umbria	3	0	0	2	0	0	1	1	0	7
Valle d'Aosta	0	1	1	2	1	0	0	2	0	7
Veneto	3	2	1	3	0	0	0	1	0	10
	32	49	18	38	45	17	39	47	15	

Source: Own elaboration based on information provided by the surveying company.

Table A23. Database records by effect of contact in Italy

Records not contacted:	
Busy	287
No answer	703
Voice mail/answering machine	58
	1048
Records contacted:	
Completed interviews, which were included in the final database	300
Completed interviews that were rejected as a result of quality control	0
Does not meet the criteria (sector)	383
Refusal to participate in the study	431
Appointments	526
CAWI survey request	12
	1652

Source: Own elaboration based on information provided by the surveying company.

4. SPAIN

Table A24. Average duration of interviews in Spain

	Average
Average time if firm employs foreigners, n=206	26.68
Average time if firm does not employ foreigners, n=95	20.51
Average time overall	24.74

Source: Own elaboration based on information provided by the surveying company.

Table A25. Median interview duration in Spain

	Median
Median for Agriculture	23.55
Median for Food processing	23.81
Median for Food service	20.60
Overall median	21.98

Source: Own elaboration based on information provided by the surveying company.

Table A26. Distribution of interviews by day in Italy:

	Number of interviews
April 16	5
April 17	10
April 18	10
April 19	5
April 23	24
April 24	30
April 25	5
April 26	6
April 28	24
April 29	20
April 30	40
May 1	24
May 2	33
May 3	10
May 5	28

May 6	22
May 7	5

Source: Own elaboration based on information provided by the surveying company.

Sector	Agriculture			Food Processing			Food service			
	1-9	10-29	30-49	1-9	10-29	30-49	1-9	10-29	30-49	
Number of employees										
Region										
Albacete	1	0	0	0	2	3	0	2	1	9
Alicante	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	2	2	7
Almeria	0	0	0	0	1	1	0	1	0	3
Badajoz	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1
Baleares	1	3	0	0	2	2	0	3	3	14
Barcelona	3	3	1	0	6	3	4	2	3	25
Bizkaia	0	0	0	0	1	2	0	4	0	7
Cantabria	0	2	1	0	0	2	0	3	0	8
Ciudad Real	0	0	1	1	1	0	0	3	0	6
Cordoba	4	2	2	1	3	3	2	1	0	18
Cuenca	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1
Gerona	1	3	0	1	4	0	0	3	1	13
Granada	1	1	1	0	3	2	0	0	0	8
Guadalajara	0	2	1	0	0	0	0	1	1	5
Huelva	0	2	0	0	3	2	1	0	1	9
Huesca	2	3	0	0	0	2	0	0	0	7
Jaen	0	0	1	0	1	1	0	0	0	3
La Coruña	0	0	1	0	2	1	1	1	0	6
Lerida	1	3	3	0	3	1	1	3	0	15
Lugo	0	1	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	3
Madrid	2	4	6	1	6	5	4	7	4	39
Malaga	0	0	0	0	1	1	1	5	0	8
Murcia	1	2	0	0	2	2	2	0	1	10
	1	0	0	0	1	2	0	4	1	9
Orense	0	0	3	0	1	0	1	0	0	5
Palmas (Las)	0	2	0	0	2	1	0	6	1	12
Pontevedra	1	1	2	0	0	0	1	0	0	5
Salamanca	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	1	0	3
Segovia	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	1
Sevilla	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	4	0	6
Tarragona	0	1	0	0	1	0	1	2	0	5
Tenerife	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1
Toledo	0	1	0	0	3	0	1	2	1	8
Valencia	1	2	3	0	3	1	0	0	1	11
Valladolid	0	0	1	1	1	0	0	1	0	4
Zamora	0	2	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	3
Zaragoza	0	0	1	0	0	1	0	1	0	3
	23	45	30	5	56	39	20	62	21	

Source: Own elaboration based on information provided by the surveying company.

Table A28. Database records by effect of contact in Spain

Records not contacted:	
Busy	277
No answer	936
Voice mail/answering machine	83
	1296
Records contacted:	
Completed interviews, which were included in the final database	301
Completed interviews that were rejected as a result of quality control	0
Does not meet the criteria (sector)	352
Refusal to participate in the study	590
Appointments	759
CAWI survey request	2
	2004

Source: Own elaboration based on information provided by the surveying company.

Deliverable information

Schedule Information	
Title and number	Report on the implementation of the survey with employers
Work Package, Task and Deliverable	Deliverable 6.1
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Report on the implementation of the survey with employers

Deliverable 6.1

About DignityFIRM

Towards becoming sustainable and resilient societies we must address the structural contradictions between our societies' exclusion of migrant workers and their substantive role in producing our food.

www.dignityfirm.eu

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